

Report on socio-economic status quo (needs and resources)

SPOKE N 4 – Montagna Digitale e Sostenibile

DELIVERABLE N10 INTERFACE

RM2 - Competitiveness of economic activities and valorization

of natural and cultural assets in mountain and remote areas

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides a summary of the main socio-economic features and trends that characterize two Alpine valleys, located in the Piedmont region: the Varaita Valley and the Pellice Valley. Through the analysis of a wide set of indicators and measures, we find that the demographic and socio-economic status quo of the two valleys have several needs/criticalities and resources/opportunities. The former include the need to increase access to higher education, to improve local mobility, to prevent foreclosures of services currently active, to improve the access to broadband internet connection (especially in the Varaita Valley), and to re-boost the tourism industry. Among the resources and opportunities, there is the dynamism of an area that is changing, both from a demographic and a socio-economic point of view, with encouraging signs of resilience and recovery after the COVID-19 pandemic crisis.

A) Introduction

Mountainous areas play an important role in the European and Italian economies, societies, and environments. They are home to a significant portion of the population, and they provide a range of goods and services, including food, water, energy, and recreation. However, if the one hand these regions have a number of strengths, including natural beauty, rich culture and heritage, and renewable energy potential on the other hand they face a number of challenges, including (IRES, 2022):

Demographic Decline

One of the biggest challenges facing mountainous areas is demographic decline. This is due to a number of factors, including the lack of employment opportunities, the aging population, and the outmigration of young people. The result is a shrinking population and an aging workforce. This can make it difficult to maintain essential services and infrastructure, and it can also lead to a loss of cultural vitality.

Economic Underdevelopment

Mountainous areas are generally economically underdeveloped compared to the rest of Europe and Italy. This is due to a number of factors, including the difficulty of access, the harsh climate, and the lack of resources. As a result, mountainous areas often have lower levels of employment, income, and productivity. They are also more likely to have higher levels of poverty and unemployment.

Limited Infrastructure

Mountainous areas often have limited infrastructure, such as roads, schools, and hospitals. This can make it difficult to attract businesses and residents to the region. It can also make it difficult to provide essential services to the population. For example, students in mountainous areas may have to travel long distances to attend school, and patients may have to travel long distances to access healthcare.

Environmental Vulnerability

Mountainous areas are particularly vulnerable to environmental challenges, such as climate change and natural disasters. Climate change is causing glaciers to melt and snowpacks to shrink, which is impacting water resources and agriculture. Natural disasters, such as landslides and floods, can also cause significant damage to infrastructure and communities.

Opportunities

In Italy, the socio-economic status quo of mountainous areas is of particular relevance for national policies as mountains represent about 58% of the country's surface, are home to about 18% of the population, and they account for about the 16% of the country's GDP (Censis, 2003). The Italian government has a number of policies in place to support the development of mountainous regions. These include (i) financial incentives for businesses and residents to locate in mountainous regions, (ii) investment in infrastructure development, such as roads, schools, and hospitals, and (iii) support for sustainable development initiatives. Despite the challenges they face, mountainous areas also offer a number of opportunities. For example, mountainous areas are home to a wealth of natural resources, such as forests, water, and minerals. They also have a rich culture and heritage. This can be a valuable asset for tourism and for attracting new businesses and residents. In addition, mountainous areas have significant renewable energy potential, a fundamental asset necessary to help to reduce the country's reliance on fossil fuels. The future of mountainous areas in Europe and Italy will depend on how these challenges and opportunities are addressed. It is important to support the sustainable development of these regions in order to ensure that they can continue to thrive, but, at the same time, it is fundamental to address the issue of demographic decline in mountainous areas. Of course, this entails improving the availability of jobs, housing, and other essential services in harmony with the preservation of the environment and the existing cultural heritage. This can be done by addressing the challenges and capitalizing on the opportunities, mountainous areas in Europe and Italy can continue to be vibrant and prosperous regions.

B) Study Area and Methodology

The Varaita Valley and the Pellice Valley are two parallel valleys in the Cottian Alps of Piedmont, Italy. They are both relatively short and narrow valleys, with the Varaita Valley being about 50 km long and the Pellice Valley being about 40 km long. The valleys are flanked by high mountains, with peaks reaching over 3,000 meters above sea level. They are both glacially formed valleys, with long, U-shaped troughs and steep valley sides. The Varaita Valley is the more southerly of the two valleys, and it is drained by the Varaita River. The Pellice Valley is the more northerly of the two valleys, and it is drained by the Pellice River.

Geomorphological context

Both valleys are characterized by a variety of geomorphological features, including glacial moraines (ridges of sediment that were deposited by glaciers), glacial lakes (formed when glaciers melt and leave behind depressions in the landscape) such as Lago di Pontechianale and Lago di Luserna, cirques (bowl-shaped depressions that were carved by glaciers), and hanging valleys (that are suspended above the main valley floor). The steep valley sides in the Varaita and Pellice Valleys are susceptible to rockfalls and landslides, events that can be triggered by heavy rainfall, earthquakes, or other factors. The majority of the rocks in the Varaita and Pellice Valleys are metamorphic rocks. These rocks were originally sedimentary rocks, but they have been transformed by heat and pressure. The most common metamorphic rocks in the valleys are schists and gneisses. There are also a number of intrusive rocks in the Varaita and Pellice Valleys. These rocks were formed when molten magma intruded into the metamorphic rocks. The most common intrusive rocks in the valleys are granites and diorites. The rocks in the Varaita and Pellice Valleys have been folded and faulted as a result of the Alpine Orogeny (the mountain-building process that created the Alps). The folds and faults in the valleys can be seen in the outcrops of rock along the valley sides. The geomorphological and geological features of the Varaita and Pellice Valleys make them a popular destination for geologists and geomorphologists and also for a popular tourist destination, with their beautiful scenery and opportunities for hiking, skiing, and other outdoor activities.

Geographical characterization

The Varaita Valley is located at the crossroads of two important mountain passes: the Colle dell'Agnello and the Colle delle Traversette. These passes connect the Varaita Valley to the Queyras Valley in France and the Valle Maira in Italy. Saluzzo is one of the nearest towns to the Varaita Valley. It is located approximately 30 to 40 kilometers to the east of the valley, depending on the specific location within the valley. The primary connection between Saluzzo and the Varaita Valley is by the road (SS22) that also connects Cuneo, the provincial capital, which is located roughly 50 to 60 kilometers to the south of the Varaita Valley. The distance from Turin to the valley is approximately 100 kilometers.

The Pellice Valley is located in the southwestern part of the Province (Metropolitan City, MC) of Turin. It is bordered by the Chisone and Germanasca Valleys to the north, and the Po Valley to the south. The major town in the nearby of the Pellice Valley is Pinerolo (around 17 kilometers). The distance between Turin and the Pellice Valley varies depending on the specific location within the valley. It is approximately 50 to 60 kilometers from Turin to the heart of the Pellice Valley, where the town of Torre Pellice is located.

The Pellice Valley is connected to Turin via Pinerolo, through an highway (A55), and several bus connections. Effective road, train, and bus connections make the Pellice Valley relatively accessible from Turin, and the scenic beauty of the valley, its historical sites, and its cultural heritage make it a popular destination for both day trips and longer visits from Turin.

Administrative organization and study area selection

Most of the municipalities of the study area are part of a kind of administrative organization called "Mountain Union" (Unione Montana) which serves as a local government structure that manages and coordinates various services and activities for the municipalities within its territory, including administrative functions, territorial planning, social services, infrastructure and transportation.

Figure 1. Study Area.

Source: own elaboration based on map from GeoPiemonte (2023).

The Unione Montana of the Pellice Valley includes the municipalities of Angrogna, Bibiana, Bobbio Pellice, Bricherasio, Luserna San Giovanni, Lusernetta, Prarostino, Roletto, Rorà, San Secondo di Pinerolo, San Pietro Val Lenina, Torre Pellice, Villar Pellice (UNCEN, 2022). The Unione Montana of the Varaita Valley includes the following municipalities: Bellino, Brossasco, Costigliole Saluzzo, Frassinò, Isasca, Melle, Piasco, Pontechianale, Rossana, Sampeyre, Venasca, Verzuolo (ibid.). In designing the study, we decided to select most of the municipalities included in the two "mountain communities", but because of the fact that a few municipalities are outside the administrative organizations, while others are members and are located too far

from the geographical region of the valley, we made several changes. The municipalities included in the analysis for the Pellice Valley are: Angrogna, Bibiana, Bobbio Pellice, Bricherasio, Campiglione Fenile, Cavour, Luserna San Giovanni, Lusernetta, Prarostino, Rorà, San Secondo, Torre Pellice, Villar Pellice. For the Varaita Valley, we included the following municipalities: Bellino, Brossasco, Busca, Casteldelfino, Costigliole Saluzzo, Frassinò, Isasca, Melle, Piasco, Pontechianale, Rossana, Sampeyre, Venasca, Verzuolo (fig. 1).

Methodology

We analyzed the socio-economic characteristics of the municipalities individuated in the study area through descriptive statistics. We collected municipal-level data from different sources and we represented it through tables, graphs and maps, including, whenever possible, time series. A comprehensive list of the variables used to perform the analysis is provided below:

Tab. 1. List of variables included in the analysis

Demography:

Population (total), 2019-2023;
Population (annual change), 2019-2023;
Natural population balance, 2020, 2021;
Migration balance, 2020, 2021;
Total population balance, 2020, 2021;
Average size of households, 2020, 2021;
Foreign population (as % of total population), 2019-2023;
Average age, 2022;
Old Age Index, 2022;
Aging Index, 2022;
Structural Dependency Ratio, 2022;
Population by Sex and Age, 2022;

Education and social services:

Rate of illiteracy, 2021;
People without educational qualifications, 2021;
Primary school diploma, 2021;
Middle school diploma, 2021;
Secondary education diploma, 2021;
Tertiary degree, 2021;
Number of schools, 2018;
Outdated schools, 2018;
People leaving their municipality on a daily basis for education (percentage), 2019;
Pre-school and childhood services facilities, 2021;
Pre-school and childhood services users, 2021;
Municipal expenditures in social services, 2020;

Health, commerce, and other services:

Family physicians, 2023;
Pharmacies, 2022;
Grocery shops, 2005-2018;

Medium-sized department stores, 2005-2018;

Large department stores, 2005-2018;

Large specialized retailers, 2005-2018;

Local markets, 2005-2018;

ATMs, 2020;

Gas stations, 2023;

Post offices, 2023;

Income and economic variables:

Active population, 2021;

Unemployment rate, 2021;

Students, 2021;

Housewives/housemakers, 2021;

Number of active companies per economic sector, 2009-2021;

Number of farms by economic sales class, 2023;

People leaving their municipality on a daily basis for work (percentage), 2019;

Motor vehicles, 2022;

Employees per economic sector, 2023;

Average income per capita, 2021;

Homes and apartments (in use and abandoned), 2021;

Accommodation facilities, 2012-2022;

Number of tourists (from Italy), 2010-2022;

Number of tourists (from other countries), 2010-2022;

Average time spent by tourists in accommodation facilities, 2010-2022;

Number of families with access to broadband internet connection (basic, >30mbps, >100mbps), 2019

C) Socio-Economic Status Quo

Italy is an aging society, with a fertility rate below replacement level, at 1.25 children per woman. The mortality rate is declining, but it is still higher than the birth rate; as a result of these trends, the Italian population is shrinking. The Italian population is also becoming more concentrated in urban areas (in 2022, 68.9% of Italians lived in urban areas). This trend is expected to continue in the coming years. The Alps are also an aging region, with a fertility rate also below replacement level, at 1.2 children per woman. These phenomena are major demographic trends encompassing the national, the regional, the provincial and the local scales (tab. 2).

Tab. 2. Total Population, 2019-2023. Study area, Italy, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr.

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
<i>Italy</i>	59816673	59641488	59236213	59030133	58850717
<i>Piedmont</i>	4328565	4311217	4274945	4256350	4240736
<i>Turin MC</i>	2238663	2230946	2219206	2208370	2198237
Angrogna	862	846	838	827	810
Bibiana	3455	3470	3392	3378	3358
Bobbio Pellice	542	547	537	539	536
Bricherasio	4629	4593	4564	4616	4623
Campiglione Fenile	1334	1339	1333	1330	1313
Cavour	5483	5480	5385	5374	5425
Luserna San Giovanni	7253	7262	7096	7162	7163
Lusemetta	499	509	492	480	493
Prarostino	1288	1265	1250	1255	1246
Rorà	236	231	228	227	225
San Secondo di Pinerolo	3647	3677	3615	3597	3637
Torre Pellice	4552	4497	4554	4591	4575
Villar Pellice	1074	1061	1045	1047	1059
Val Pellice	34854	34777	34329	34423	34463
<i>Cuneo Pr</i>	587213	586113	581798	580155	579948
Bellino	106	102	97	95	100
Brossasco	1065	1031	1009	1005	993
Busca	10082	10114	10078	10127	10144
Casteldelfino	154	151	152	143	142
Costigliole Saluzzo	3297	3314	3333	3295	3312
Frassino	269	270	264	262	253
Isasca	84	78	75	72	69
Melle	290	286	292	298	300
Piasco	2763	2770	2703	2696	2713
Pontechianale	165	167	175	187	183
Rossana	867	833	809	820	826
Sampeyre	996	1004	989	988	998
Venasca	1386	1383	1352	1348	1335
Verzuolo	6428	6417	6463	6417	6376
Valle Varaita	27952	27920	27791	27753	27744

Source: own elaboration based D2 on ISTAT (2023).

Total Population 2019-2023

The demographic trends in Italy and the Alps are already having a significant impact on society and the economy. The aging population is putting a strain on social security and healthcare systems. The shrinking population is leading to a decline in the workforce and a decrease in tax revenues. As of 2023, the Pellice Valley counts 34,463 inhabitants (1.6% of the population of the Metropolitan City of Turin), while the Varaita Valley totaled 27,744 inhabitants (4.8% of the population of the Province of Cuneo). The major towns (with a population higher than 4,000) of the former are Luserna San Giovanni (7,163), Cavour (5,425) and Torre Pellice (4,575), and Bricherasio (4,623). In the Varaita Valley, more than half of the population lives in Busca (10,144), Verzuolo (6,376), and Costigliole Saluzzo (3,312) which are located in the plane at the entrance of the Valley. Demographic trends show that the major tendencies at play at the national and regional levels also emerge in the study area, where in the last five years (2019-2023) the population has declined (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Demographic trends for Italy, Piedmont, Varaita Valley and Pellice Valley. Total population (2019 = 1). 2019-2023.

Source: own elaboration based D2 on ISTAT (2023).

However, whilst the steepest decline for all the areas has been recorded in the midst of the COVID-19 crisis (2019-2021), it should be noted how the population in the Pellice Valley rebounded after 2021, while in the case of the Varaita Valley stabilized, in contrast with the negative trends observed for both Italy and Piedmont.

Population dynamics

The examination of the most recent demographic indicators available (tab. 3), shows some relevant features of the process highlighted in fig. 2, namely: (i) the predominance of negative natural population balances, with the exception of Pontechianale, in the Varaita Valley; (ii) the predominance of positive migration balances, especially in the Pellice Valley; (iii) the negative total population balance for each of the territories considered, with a few exceptions where positive rates of immigration offset the natural decline of the population (i.e., Torre Pellice, Melle, and Pontechianale). Interestingly, the average size of households in these municipalities is lower than the local, provincial and regional averages, indicating, on one hand, a possible phenomenon of immigration of single individuals, and on the other hand, a predominance of single elderly people living alone.

Tab. 3. Natural population balance, migration balance, total population balance as percentage of total population, and average size of households, 2021. Study area, Italy, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr. Cells color indicate magnitude of change (dark red $\leq -1\%$; red $<0 < -1\%$; white = 0%; green $>0 < 1\%$; dark green $\geq 0\%$).

	Natural population balance	Migration balance	Total population balance	Average size of households
Piedmont	-0.90%	0.11%	-0.79%	2.1
Turin MC	-0.80%	0.13%	-0.67%	2.1
Angrogna	-1.19%	0.24%	-0.95%	2.0
Bibiana	-0.87%	0.15%	-0.73%	2.2
Bobbio Pellice	-0.37%	-1.29%	-1.66%	1.9
Bricherasio	-0.52%	0.35%	-0.17%	2.2
Campiglione Fenile	-0.60%	0.45%	-0.15%	2.3
Cavour	-1.33%	0.06%	-1.27%	2.2
Luserna San Giovanni	-1.87%	0.52%	-1.35%	2.0
Lusernetta	-1.00%	-2.20%	-3.20%	2.1
Prarostino	-1.99%	1.27%	-0.72%	2.2
Rorà	-0.87%	0.00%	-0.87%	2.0
San Secondo di Pinerolo	-0.93%	0.80%	-0.14%	2.2
Torre Pellice	-1.79%	3.23%	1.44%	1.9
Villar Pellice	-1.71%	1.80%	0.09%	2.0
Val Pellice	-1.29%	0.76%	-0.53%	2.1
Provincia di Cuneo	-0.74%	0.13%	-0.61%	2.2
Bellino	-2.83%	-0.94%	-3.77%	1.6
Brossasco	-1.50%	0.94%	-0.56%	2.0
Busca	-0.39%	0.03%	-0.36%	2.2
Casteldelfino	-1.95%	0.00%	-1.95%	1.7
Costigliole Saluzzo	-0.70%	0.70%	0.00%	2.3
Frassinò	-2.23%	0.37%	-1.86%	1.7
Isasca	-1.19%	-2.38%	-3.57%	1.7
Melle	0.00%	2.76%	2.76%	1.7
Piasco	-1.38%	-0.22%	-1.59%	2.2
Pontechianale	0.61%	4.85%	5.45%	1.6
Rossana	-1.85%	-0.58%	-2.42%	2.0
Sampeyre	-2.31%	1.41%	-0.90%	1.9
Venasca	-0.72%	-0.79%	-1.52%	2.1
Verzuolo	-0.79%	0.98%	0.19%	2.3
Valle Varaita	-0.80%	0.38%	-0.43%	2.2

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

A closer look to the dynamics of population change in the study area, reveals how total population balances tend to vary over time, with over-magnified effects for those municipalities inhabited by few hundreds of people (fig. 3). On one hand, all the major changes recorded over the period observed are negative (-5% or less), raising concerns about the severity of the ongoing processes of depopulation.

Fig. 3. Total population balance as percentage of total population, a) 2019-2020, b) 2020-2021, c) 2021-2022, d) 2022-2023. Study area. Color indicate magnitude of change (see legends).

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

On the other hand, these major changes involved very small municipalities (Bellino, Isasca, and Casteldelfino) for only one period, whereas in the other periods the phenomenon has been less intense or even reverted. In opposition with these trends involving small municipalities in the inner areas of the valleys, the largest towns located between the plane and the valley, show a trend that is more or less stable, if even positive, especially in the case of the Varaita Valley.

An important element of the migration balance is the immigration of foreign nationals. Fig. 4 shows the percentage of inhabitants with foreign citizenship between 2019 and 2023. As it can be seen, such an indicator has been quite stable over the period considered in Italy, in Piedmont, and in the metropolitan city of Turin. However, it increased in the Province of Cuneo, in the Varaita Valley, and to a lower extent in the Pellice Valley. The percentage of foreign nationals living in the Varaita Valley is particularly high, higher even than the national, regional and provincial averages. On the contrary, the Val Pellice has a lower concentration of foreign nationals, about four percentage points less than the Varaita Valley, and about 2 percentage points less than the average for the Metropolitan City of Turin. This last element is of interest because it signals how migration balances in the two study areas might represent different phenomena: the first, taking place in the Pellice Valley, might be driven by the immigration of nationals from the rest of the Metropolitan City of Turin or the Piedmont region, thus constituting an example of re-population through the formation of a new type of mountain population (Pettenati, 2013).

Fig. 4. Foreign nationals (as % of total population) for Italy, Piedmont, Varaita Valley and Pellice Valley. Total population (2019 = 1). 2019-2023.

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

The second, involving the municipalities of the Varaita Valley, seems to be driven more by the immigration of foreign nationals rather than nationals coming from the rest of the Province of Cuneo or the Piedmont region. However, the distribution of foreign nationals within the municipalities of the study area is highly uneven (fig. 5). Luserna San Giovanni (Pellice Valley), Costigliole Saluzzo, and Verzuolo (Varaita Valley) are the primary attractors for foreign nationals, who constitute a share between 10% and 20% of the total population. In the case of the Varaita Valley this might be due to the high demand for agricultural workers in the flatland around the town of Saluzzo. However, several municipalities in both valleys have a concentration of foreign nationals similar to the national average, whereas inner areas tend to have a much lower concentration.

Fig. 5. Foreign nationals (as % of total population). Study area, 2023.

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

Population structure

A characteristics emerging from the demographic profiles of the study areas, is that each Valley tends to reflect the average demographic characteristics of the provincial context (Metropolitan City of Turin for the Pellice Valley, and the Province of Cuneo for the Varaita Valley). This observation applies also to the structure of the population (tab. 4).

Tab. 4. Average age, old age index, aging index, and structural dependency ratio. Study area, Italy, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr, 2022.

	Av. Age	Old age index	Aging index	Structural dependency index
<i>Italy</i>	45.90	24	1.93	0.58
<i>Piedmont</i>	47.30	26	2.25	0.62
<i>Turin MC</i>	47.15	26	2.21	0.62
Val Pellice	47.67	27	2.32	0.64
<i>Cuneo Pr</i>	45.98	25	1.94	0.60
Valle Varaita	45.67	25	1.91	0.60

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

The difference between the two study areas is relevant for what pertains all the indicators presented in tab. 4. In particular, the Pellice Valley, in line with the provincial values, shows higher average age, old age index (population aged 65 years and over per 100 people), aging index (population aged 65 years and over per each individual aged between 0 and 14 years old), and structural dependency ratio than the Varaita Valley. The latter, by contrast, has a population structure that is similar to the rest of the Province of Cuneo (tab. 5, fig. 6).

Tab. 5. Population structure by age group and sex. Study area, Italy, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr, 2022.

	Age group	Italy	Piedmont	Turin MC	Pellice Valley	Cuneo Pr	Varaita Valley
Females	0-35	32.2%	30.2%	30.2%	30.1%	32.9%	32.9%
	36-65	42.7%	42.2%	42.4%	41.8%	41.4%	41.0%
	65+	25.1%	27.6%	27.4%	28.1%	25.7%	26.1%
Males	0-35	35.9%	34.0%	34.3%	33.2%	36.0%	35.5%
	36-65	43.7%	43.5%	43.3%	43.1%	42.7%	42.5%
	65+	20.4%	22.5%	22.3%	23.8%	21.3%	22.0%

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

However, each municipality within each valley is characterized by a demographic structure that can deviate significantly from the local average (fig. 7).

Fig. 6. Population by Sex (percentages; orange for females, and light orange for males) and age, 2022.

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

Fig. 7. Demographic structure, a) average age; b) old age index; c) aging index; d) structural dependency ratio. Study area, 2023.

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

Fig. 6 shows a particular feature of the populations living in the study area: although the indicators tend to change from the entrance to the end of the two valleys, they also are much more homogeneous in the case of the Pellice Valley than the Varaita one. The discrepancy is related to the remoteness of the towns and villages located in the end of the valley, which might be perceived as a barrier for young households planning to settle in the valley.

Social Context

The social context in the mountainous regions of Piedmont is diverse and varies depending on the specific valley and community. However, there are some general trends that can be observed. Traditionally, the Piedmont valleys have been rural and agricultural communities, although in many contexts there has been a shift towards urbanization and tourism in the past decades. This has led to a change in the social fabric of many communities, with an influx of new residents and a relative decline in the traditional way of life. Depopulation and (partial) repopulation are phenomena shaping not only the identity of the valleys, but also the availability and accessibility of adequate services and infrastructures (e.g., see D14 and D16), the possibility to supply in a financially-sustainable way local needs, and to adequately support the development of strategic assets and resources.

Education

Education and human capital are essential for the development of mountainous areas. They can help to promote economic growth by increasing the productivity of the workforce and attracting new industries or encouraging the opening of new businesses. In addition, a well-educated population is more likely to help to create a more attractive environment for young households relocating outside of cities. Education is also important to improve the health and well-being of individuals, or to allow them to fully exploit the potential of new devices and technologies allowing for the digital delivery of basic services.

Tab. 6. Rate of illiteracy; People without educational qualifications (percentage of population 9+ y.o.). Study area, Italy, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr, 2022.

	Rate of illiteracy	People without educational qualifications	Primary school diploma	Middle school diploma	Secondary education diploma	Tertiary degree
<i>Italy</i>	0.5%	4.2%	14.9%	29.1%	36.3%	11.4%
<i>Piedmont</i>	0.4%	3.6%	14.9%	30.5%	36.7%	10.1%
<i>Turin MC</i>	0.4%	3.8%	13.6%	29.8%	37.0%	11.6%
Angrogna		3.0%	15.5%	37.1%	32.2%	8.4%
Bibiana	0.4%	5.2%	17.2%	32.8%	36.4%	5.6%
Bobbio Pellice	0.2%	2.2%	20.1%	32.7%	35.7%	6.3%
Bricherasio	0.2%	3.6%	15.5%	32.9%	36.5%	7.5%
Campiglione Fenile	0.2%	3.8%	17.6%	35.9%	34.1%	5.3%
Cavour	0.6%	3.7%	19.1%	35.0%	33.1%	6.0%
Luserna San Giovanni	0.7%	4.2%	16.7%	33.3%	35.5%	7.1%
Lusernetta		3.6%	18.9%	36.5%	30.3%	5.1%
Prarostino	0.3%	3.4%	15.3%	31.3%	35.9%	9.6%
Rorà	0.5%	1.8%	16.1%	36.9%	37.3%	4.6%
San Secondo di Pinerolo	0.1%	3.2%	15.7%	28.8%	36.9%	11.2%
Torre Pellice	0.4%	3.3%	13.5%	30.2%	37.7%	10.7%
Villar Pellice	0.2%	3.5%	17.6%	33.9%	37.2%	5.2%
Pellice Valley	0.4%	3.8%	16.5%	32.8%	35.7%	7.7%
<i>Cuneo Pr</i>	0.3%	3.3%	16.7%	31.8%	36.0%	8.0%
Bellino			20.4%	41.9%	31.2%	3.2%
Brossasco	0.1%	2.6%	23.3%	34.9%	32.8%	3.6%
Busca	0.3%	3.4%	17.0%	33.8%	34.9%	6.4%
Casteldelfino	0.7%	2.2%	25.4%	27.6%	39.6%	3.0%
Costigliole Saluzzo	0.4%	4.2%	18.7%	35.9%	33.6%	4.7%
Frassino	0.4%	1.6%	22.6%	29.8%	35.1%	7.7%
Isasca	1.6%	6.3%	35.9%	35.9%	18.8%	3.1%
Melle		2.2%	20.9%	32.6%	34.1%	7.0%
Piasco	0.1%	2.4%	21.0%	34.1%	32.5%	5.5%
Pontechianale		1.1%	21.3%	32.0%	34.8%	5.6%
Rossana	0.1%	3.4%	18.3%	35.2%	35.8%	5.1%
Sampeyre	0.2%	3.1%	16.8%	34.9%	36.2%	5.5%
Venasca	0.3%	3.1%	17.6%	38.4%	31.8%	6.5%

Verzuolo	0.3%	3.7%	17.3%	32.5%	36.2%	6.4%
Varaita Valley	0.3%	3.4%	18.2%	34.1%	34.6%	5.9%

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

In terms of illiteracy rates, as well as the proportion of individuals without educational qualifications, the population inhabiting the study areas is in line with the provincial averages, which, in turn, are lower than the national average (tab. 6). On the contrary, the percentage of people with higher education (secondary and tertiary degrees) is smaller in the study area than provincial, regional or national averages., while the opposite is true for the proportion of population with lower levels of education (primary and middle schools). However, the low proportion of people with higher education varies significantly among the municipalities of the two valleys (fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Proportion of people with tertiary degrees. Study area, 2022.

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

Interestingly, the area with the highest concentration of tertiary degrees, is the northern side of the Pellice Valley, between the municipalities of Torre Pellice, Angrogna, Prarostino, San Secondo di Pinerolo e Bricherasio. In the Varaita Valley, by contrast, only the municipality of Frassinio comes close to the provincial average, whereas for the other municipalities the figures are significantly lower. Such characteristics might be related to the degree of accessibility of education facilities in the valleys, and outside of them. For what pertains basic education services, both valleys have several schools, although the Pellice Valley, which is the most populated one, has less facilities than the Varaita Valley (27 vs. 29). The ratio between the population aged 6-16 years old, and the number of schools is 162 for the Metropolitan City of Turin, 101 for the Province of Cuneo, 111 for the Pellice Valley, and 86 for the Varaita Valley (tab. 7).

Tab. 7. Number of schools. Study area. 2018.

	Number of schools	% Outdated schools	Schools/km2	Children 6-16 y.o. per school
<i>Piedmont</i>	<i>3131</i>	<i>44%</i>	<i>0.12</i>	<i>127</i>
<i>Turin MC</i>	<i>1290</i>	<i>33%</i>	<i>0.19</i>	<i>162</i>
Angrogna	2	50%	0.05	39
Bibiana	3	33%	0.16	117
Bobbio Pellice	1	0%	0.01	45
Bricherasio	2	50%	0.09	207
Campiglione Fenile	4	25%	0.36	30
Cavour	3	0%	0.06	161
Luserna San Giovanni	5	40%	0.28	119
Lusernetta	1	0%	0.14	44
Prarostino	1	100%	0.10	119
Rorà	0	0%	0.00	0
San Secondo di Pinerolo	2	0%	0.16	178
Torre Pellice	2	50%	0.09	149
Villar Pellice	1	0%	0.02	90
Pellice Valley	27	30%	0.07	111
<i>Cunero Pr</i>	<i>576</i>	<i>48%</i>	<i>0.08</i>	<i>101</i>
Bellino	0	0%	0.00	0
Brossasco	1	100%	0.04	75
Busca	7	43%	0.09	138
Casteldelfino	0	0%	0.00	0
Costigliole Saluzzo	2	0%	0.13	146
Frassino	0	0%	0.00	0
Isasca	0	0%	0.00	0
Melle	0	0%	0.00	0
Piasco	2	50%	0.19	123
Pontechianale	0	0%	0.00	0
Rossana	1	0%	0.05	61
Sampeyre	2	0%	0.02	41
Venasca	4	50%	0.20	27
Verzuolo	10	60%	0.38	61
Varaita Valley	29	45%	0.05	86

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

In addition, schools in the Pellice Valley are more evenly distributed, with one school each 14 squared-kilometers against one each 20 squared-kilometers. Finally, public schools in the Varaita Valley are also older and 45% of them are outdated, against the 30% of the Pellice Valley.

Although primary schools are relatively evenly distributed, middle and secondary schools often are concentrated in a few municipalities, where students from the valley converge each day. The proportion of students traveling daily from their municipality to another in the same valley or outside the valley (e.g.

university students) is significantly higher in the study area than in the provincial, regional or national averages (fig. 9).

Fig. 9. People leaving their municipality on a daily basis for education (percentage). Study area, Italy, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr, 2019.

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

Because of demographic and morphological reasons, the schooling system in the study area might be defined as “expensive” both for the administrations (low population density challenging the financial sustainability of small facilities) and the students (high expenditures in terms of time and resources to travel between home and school). The Pellice Valley’s high share of students traveling daily within the valley and out of it, can also benefit from public transportation services and infrastructures that the Varaita Valley does not possess. If the “expensiveness” of the schooling system can be considered as a major barrier to the attraction of young households to the valleys, so should be considered the number and the distribution of pre-schooling facilities in the area.

Pre-schooling facilities

In spite of their different demographic size, the two valleys of the study area have a similar population in age 0-3 years old (around 800 individuals). Of course, given its size and its demographic weight, the Pellice Valley has more pre-schooling facilities than the Varaita one. However, the number of facilities with respect to the target population is not only higher than that of the Varaita Valley, but it is higher than the regional and provincial averages (fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Pre-school and childhood service facilities. Study area, Italy, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr, 2021.

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

However, in terms of places authorized, the capacity of the facilities of the Pellice Valley is in line with the regional and provincial ones, whereas the authorized places in the Varaita Valley cover only around the 16% of the target population (a value in line with the Province of Cuneo average).

Social Services

The municipalities in the study area are equipped to provide different social services to a multitude of users, including family and children, people with disabilities, people with addictions, elderly people, immigrants, Roma, Sinti and Caminanti, people in poverty, adult hardship and homelessness. The resources allocated to each service depend on the municipality and its specific issues. Fig. 11 provides a comparison between the municipal expenditures of the municipalities in the study area, the Metropolitan City of Turin, the Province of Cuneo and the Piedmont Region.

Fig. 11. Municipal expenditures in social services (€ per target population). Study area, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr, 2020.

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

Relative expenditures are not an adequate indicator to measure the performance of social services providers, however, fig. 11 shows a few interesting insights: although significantly lower than the provincial average, two municipalities in the Pellice Valley have expenditures higher than the other municipalities in the study area: Villar Pellice and Torre Pellice. One of the reasons that might explain this, possibly lies in the cultural and historical heritage of the Waldensian identity.

Family physicians and pharmacies

The main health facilities in the study area are located in Torre Pellice (Pellice Valley, community hospital) and Verzuolo (Varaita Valley, “casa della salute”). Although very important, the variety of health services offered by these structures is nevertheless limited, therefore people from the Varaita Valley need to travel to Saluzzo (about 30 kilometers from Frassino) to get full hospital services, while inhabitants of the Pellice Valley have to travel to Pinerolo (about 20 kilometers from Torre Pellice). However, health care services in the study area are carried on first and foremost by family physicians, who are a fundamental component of the local health care system. As of 2023, there are 41 family physicians in the Pellice Valley and 42 in the Varaita Valley (tab. 8).

Tab. 8. Number of family physicians (2023) and pharmacies (2022). Study area and Piedmont.

	Family Physicians	Population per physician	Pharmacies	Pharmacies per 1000 people
Angrogna	1	838	0	0

Bibiana	5	678	1	0.3
Bobbio pellice	2	269	1	1.9
Bricherasio	4	1141	1	0.2
Campiglione fenile	2	667	1	0.8
Cavour	5	1077	2	0.4
Luserna san giovanni	7	1014	2	0.3
Lusernetta	0	0	0	0.0
Prarostino	2	625	0	0.0
Rorà	0	0	0	0.0
San secondo di Pinerolo	3	1205	1	0.3
Torre Pellice	8	569	2	0.4
Villar Pellice	2	523	1	1.0
Pellice Valley	41	837	12	0.3
Bellino	0	0	0	0.0
Brossasco	2	505	1	1.0
Busca	9	1120	3	0.3
Casteldelfino	2	76		0.0
Costigliole saluzzo	3	1111	1	0.3
Frassino	1	264		0.0
Isasca	1	75		0.0
Melle	1	292	1	3.4
Piasco	3	901	1	0.4
Pontechianale	1	175		0.0
Rossana	1	809	1	1.2
Sampeyre	3	330	1	1.0
Venasca	4	338	1	0.7
Verzuolo	11	588	2	0.3
Varaita Valley	42	662	12	0.4
Piedmont	6009	711	1568	0.4

Source: own elaboration based on Regione Piemonte (2023a).

In relative terms, the ratio between population and physicians, is higher than the regional average (711) in the case of the Pellice Valley (837) and lower than the regional average in the case of the Varaita Valley (662). The supply of basic health services in the study area is complemented by 12 pharmacies in each valley, that is equivalent to 0.3 (Pellice Valley) and 0.4 (Varaita Valley), values close to the regional average (0.4).

Commerce and other services

Data on the number and type of commercial activities in the study area is available for the period 2005-2018. Unfortunately, the lack of data for the period 2019-2022 is a major limitation to the full understanding of the trends and dynamics taking place in the study area, and especially for the assessment of the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on the local availability of services. However, tab. 9 shows how the number of commercial services in the two valleys has changed between 2005 and 2018.

Tab. 9. Number of grocery shops, medium-sized department stores, large department stores, large specialized retailers, local markets (2005-2018). Study area.

	Grocery shops	Medium-sized department stores	Large department stores	Large specialized retailers	Local markets	
Pellice Valley	2005	463	0	0	1	10
	2006	470	0	0	1	10
	2007	472	0	0	1	10
	2008	467	0	0	1	10
	2009	467	0	0	1	11
	2010	468	1	0	1	11
	2011	468	1	0	1	12
	2012	463	1	0	1	11
	2013	459	1	0	1	11
	2014	447	1	0	1	11
	2015	447	1	0	1	11
	2016	450	2	0	1	11
	2017	451	2	0	1	11
	2018	453	2	0	1	11
Varaita Valley	2005	398	0	1	0	11
	2006	395	0	1	0	11
	2007	392	0	1	0	11
	2008	403	0	1	0	11
	2009	401	0	1	0	11
	2010	395	0	1	0	11
	2011	384	0	1	0	11
	2012	386	1	0	0	11
	2013	392	1	0	0	11
	2014	415	1	0	0	11
	2015	408	1	0	0	11
	2016	407	1	0	0	11
	2017	401	1	0	0	11
	2018	396	1	0	0	11

Source: own elaboration based on Regione Piemonte (2023b).

In the Pellice Valley, the bulk of commercial services (grocery shops) has slightly declined in the period considered, a decrease partially compensated by the opening of two medium-sized department stores. In the Varaita Valley, the number of grocery stores has been more or less stable around over the period considered, with a peak at 415 in 2014. Only one medium-large department store has been in activity over the same period. The number of local markets has been stable in the Varaita Valley, while it increased by 1 in the Pellice Valley. The spatial density of commercial services (per 1,000 people) in 2018 is represented in fig. 12a.

Fig. 12. Commercial and other services per 1000 people, a) grocery stores, medium-large department stores, large specialized retailers, and local markets (2018); b) ATMs (2020); c) Gas stations (2023); d) Post offices (2023). Study area, 2023.

Source: own elaboration based on various sources.

The distribution of commercial services in the study area is highly uneven, with several scarcely-populated municipalities in the ending part of the Varaita Valley counting concentration up to four times the local average. This raises concerns about the financial sustainability of small businesses in contexts of depopulation, but it also can represent an important resource for the tourism industry. The same consideration applies to the case of ATMs (fig. 12b) and gas stations (fig. 12c). In the case of postal services (fig. 12d), by contrast, the amount of facilities per 1,000 people is evenly distributed in both the valleys, except for the municipalities of Pontechianale and Bellino. However, it is important to consider how in scarcely-populated areas, the existence of postal offices is vital to maintain the access to several basic services, as well as to provide an element of social vitality for the community living there.

Economic context

The economic context in Alpine valleys is varied, but there are some general trends. The economy of many Alpine valleys is based on tourism, agriculture, and forestry. Tourism is a major source of revenue and employment in many Alpine valleys, especially during the winter months. Agriculture and forestry are also important economic sectors, but they are often challenged by the harsh climate and difficult terrain. In recent years, there has been a trend towards diversification of the economy in Alpine valleys. This is being driven by a number of factors, including the decline of traditional industries, the increasing importance of tourism, and the need to adapt to climate change. Some Alpine valleys are successfully diversifying their economies by developing new industries, such as renewable energy, technology, and creative industries. However,

other Alpine valleys are struggling to adapt to the changing economic landscape and are facing challenges such as unemployment, poverty, and outmigration.

Labor data

A first measure of the economic status quo of the study area is provided in tab. 10. On one hand, the Varaita Valley has an active population (54%) that is relatively higher than the national and regional averages (respectively 51% and 53%), but that is slightly lower than the provincial average (55%). On the other hand, the Pellice Valley has an active population (51%) that is in line with the national average, but lower than the regional and provincial ones. The unemployment rate, by contrast, is lower in both valleys than the provincial averages (8% for the Pellice Valley against 9% for the Metropolitan City of Turin, and 5% for the Varaita Valley against the 6% for the Province of Cuneo). There are, nevertheless, three municipalities located in the Pellice Valley, where the unemployment rate is significantly higher than the national, regional, and provincial averages: Torre Pellice (11%), Luserna San Giovanni (10%), and Lusernetta (10%).

Tab. 10. Active population, Unemployment rate, Students, Housewives/housemakers. Italy, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr, and Study area. 2021.

	Active population	Unemployment rate	Students	Housewives /housemakers
<i>Italy</i>	51%	9%	8.0%	11.2%
<i>Piedmont</i>	53%	8%	7.0%	7.7%
<i>Turin MC</i>	53%	9%	7.2%	7.8%
Angrogna	50%	8%	8.3%	8.4%
Bibiana	53%	8%	7.1%	7.6%
Bobbio Pellice	48%	7%	6.6%	6.7%
Bricherasio	55%	6%	6.9%	7.0%
Campiglione Fenile	54%	5%	6.1%	7.9%
Cavour	54%	6%	6.1%	7.3%
Luserna San Giovanni	47%	10%	6.4%	7.6%
Lusernetta	54%	10%	5.0%	5.4%
Prarostino	51%	9%	8.3%	7.2%
Rorà	51%	9%	4.4%	4.4%
San Secondo di Pinerolo	52%	7%	8.5%	6.5%
Torre Pellice	47%	11%	5.9%	8.4%
Villar Pellice	52%	7%	6.5%	4.4%
Pellice Valley	51%	8%	6.7%	7.3%
<i>Cuneo Pr</i>	55%	6%	6.8%	6.9%
Bellino	57%	0%	0.0%	1.1%
Brossasco	51%	4%	6.2%	6.8%
Busca	56%	5%	6.4%	6.5%
Casteldelfino	47%	9%	7.2%	4.6%
Costigliole Saluzzo	54%	6%	6.6%	8.1%
Frassinò	48%	9%	3.9%	6.8%
Isasca	45%	3%	3.7%	9.4%
Melle	52%	5%	3.8%	4.2%
Piasco	53%	5%	7.4%	5.2%

Pontechianale	53%	4%	1.2%	4.3%
Rossana	56%	5%	5.0%	5.0%
Sampeyre	52%	4%	5.0%	5.3%
Venasca	51%	5%	5.7%	8.0%
Verzuolo	54%	7%	7.3%	7.3%
Varaita Valley	54%	5%	6.5%	6.7%

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

The active population in both valleys is less keen to stay at home (housewives, housemakers) or to attend educational programs than the provincial, regional, and national averages. In other words, in both valleys (except for a few municipalities), unemployment is low, participation rates in the labor market are high, and the share of active population neither at work not at school is relatively low.

Active companies

The analysis of businesses active between 2009 and 2021 in both valleys is provided in fig. 13, where three graphs for each valley provide information about the evolution of businesses between 2009 and 2021.

Fig. 13. Companies and businesses by ATECO code active in the study area between 2009 and 2021.

Source: own elaboration based D2 on ISTAT (2023).

The first insight that fig. 13 brings up is the dynamics of economic activity (businesses openings – businesses foreclosures) observed during the period considered. Indeed, it is evident for both valleys included in the study area, how a negative trend characterized the years between 2009 and 2011, with a lowest peak that has been reached between 2012 and 2013 (the years of the debt crisis in Italy). Thereafter, and in spite of the COVID-19 pandemic crisis, the balance between openings and foreclosures has been increasing until reaching positive values between 2019 and 2021. Between 2009 and 2021, most of the companies that faced more foreclosures than new openings are farms (ATECO code A01), while the businesses with a positive balance belong to the service sector, in particular services to those services for the care of elderly people. In spite of the loss of many farms over the past few years, the agricultural sector (ATECO code A) is the one to which the majority of the economic activities in both valleys belong to.

However, it should be noted how one fourth of the existing agricultural businesses in the study area does not generate revenues sufficient to support a full-time job (tab. 11).

Tab. 11. Percentage of farms per economic size (income, €). 2023.

Income Class (€)	Pellice Valley	Varaita Valley
N.D.	2.9%	2.8%
< 10,000	24.8%	26.3%
10,000 - 15,000	9.5%	7.7%
15,000 - 30,000	18.2%	15.6%
30,000 - 45,000	9.7%	10.4%
45,000 - 60,000	7.2%	6.0%
60,000 - 85,000	8.4%	6.3%
85,000 - 100,000	4.3%	4.8%
100,000 - 150,000	7.3%	8.2%
150,000 - 200,000	3.7%	3.3%
200,000 - 250,000	2.0%	2.3%
250,000 - 500,000	1.4%	4.0%
> 500,000	0.7%	2.3%

Source: own elaboration based on ANAU (2023).

Employment

In terms of employment, the study area is characterized by two major catchments: Busca for the Varaita Valley, and Cavour for the Pellice Valley (fig. 14). From a geographical standpoint, employments in the Pellice Valley are more evenly distributed than in the Varaita Valley. The largest share of workers is employed in six municipalities, from the entrance to the middle of the valley. By contrast, the employments in the Varaita Valley are mainly concentrated at the entrance of the valley, whereas the municipalities in the mountainous part of the valley play a residual role.

Fig. 14. Employments per municipality. Study area, 2023.

Source: own elaboration based on AAEP (2023).

Indeed, almost half of the people living in the Varaita Valley travel each day to go to work in a different municipality (fig. 15). As in the case of students, also workers living in the study area use to travel more than the provincial, regional, and national averages.

Fig. 15. People leaving their municipality on a daily basis for work (percentage). Study area, Italy, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr, 2019.

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

Interestingly, this type of mobility demand that might entail higher ownership of private motor vehicles and therefore higher motorization rates, seem to have an impact only in the case of the Pellice Valley (tab. 12), where the average number of cars per household and the number of cars each 1,000 people are higher than

both the provincial and the regional averages. However, in the case of the Varaita Valley, the motorization rate is well below the provincial average, although it is higher than the national and regional ones.

Tab. 12. Motorization rate. Italy, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr, and Study area. 2022.

	N cars / household	Cars / 1000 people
<i>Italy</i>	1.53	682
<i>Piedmont</i>	1.45	683
<i>Turin MC</i>	1.37	654
Angrogna	1.45	721
Bibiana	1.59	704
Bobbio Pellice	1.31	711
Bricherasio	1.64	735
Campiglione Fenile	1.65	731
Cavour	1.70	754
Luserna San Giovanni	1.40	674
Lusernetta	1.83	865
Prarostino	1.71	759
Rorà	1.71	859
San Secondo di Pinerolo	1.71	770
Torre Pellice	1.24	658
Villar Pellice	1.52	767
Pellice Valley	1.53	719
<i>Cuneo Pr</i>	1.62	728
Bellino	1.22	747
Brossasco	1.58	793
Busca	1.59	704
Casteldelfino	1.29	769
Costigliole Saluzzo	1.59	680
Frassino	1.25	771
Isasca	1.30	778
Melle	1.29	762
Piasco	1.58	730
Pontechianale	1.19	706
Rossana	1.75	862
Sampeyre	1.46	760
Venasca	1.59	758
Verzuolo	1.50	661
Varaita Valley	1.55	708

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

The analysis of the employments per economic sector in the study area reveals some interesting characteristics of the economic context of the two valleys. On one hand, the main employment sectors are the same in both countries: agriculture (27%-33%), commerce (15%-18%), buildings (16%-17%), manufacturing (8%-9%). On the other hand it is relevant to note how, for both valleys, the hospitality sector absorbs only a tiny share of total employments (around 7%), a figure that in other mountainous contexts is much higher.

Fig. 16. Employees per economic sector. Study area. 2023.

Source: own elaboration based on AAEP (2023).

Average income and built capital

The high share of low-value added employments is reflected in the low average income of the two valleys (fig. 17). In the Varaita Valley the average income is 11% lower than in the Province of Cuneo, whereas the average income in the Pellice Valley is 16% lower than in the Metropolitan City of Turin.

Fig. 17. Average income per taxpayer. Italy, Piedmont, Turin MC, Cuneo Pr, and Study area. 2021.

Source: own elaboration based on MEF (2023).

Once more, these values tend to vary significantly across the municipalities of the study area and their position within each valley. As shown in fig. 18, the municipalities located at the end of the Varaita Valley have the lowest average income levels, while the highest ones characterize the municipalities that are more employments and more differentiated professional profiles.

Fig. 18. Average income per taxpayer. Study area. 2021.

Source: own elaboration based on MEF (2023).

Fig. 19. Percentage of abandoned homes and apartments. Study area. 2021.

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT (2023).

Interestingly, the municipalities with a tourism sector more developed than the others (i.e., Torre Pellice and Sampeyre) do not have average income levels significantly higher than the average.

From another perspective, the study area is characterized by the widespread abandonment of built capital, especially in the Varaita Valley, in all the municipalities located in the most mountainous part of the valley (fig. 19). This issue, that in many municipalities involves between 75% and 90% of existing buildings, represent an important burden, but it might also become an opportunity, if the development of some sectors of the local economy, like for instance the tourism sector, will be supported with adequate policies.

The tourism sector

In 2022 there were 101 facilities offering hospitality in the Pellice Valley, and 97 in the Varaita Valley. This was equivalent to 2,500 places in the former and 3,200 in the latter. These figures seem relatively low in comparison to other alpine valleys that during the past decades have invested decidedly in the development of the local tourism sector, but the ongoing tendencies might change the outlook for the next years.

Considering the period 2012-2022, it is relevant to highlight how the Varaita Valley, for instance, has been investing in new facilities, outpacing the regional trend and following the national one (fig. 20a).

Fig. 20. Tourism sector: accommodation facilities (a) and available places (b). Italy, Piedmont, and Study area. 2012-2022.

Source: own elaboration based on Regione Piemonte (2023).

On the contrary, over the same period, the Pellice Valley has been divesting from accommodation facilities, resulting in a decline of available places (fig. 20a,b). In this case, it could be possible that the trend followed by the Pellice Valley has been affected by the COVID-19 pandemic crisis, as before 2019 the local tourism sector had achieved a peak in the number of facilities, and after two years of contraction (2019-2020), the sector begun to show signs of resilience in 2021-2022. However, in spite of the crisis in the supply of tourism services in the Pellice Valley, the trends for what pertains the demand in both valleys is not positive (fig. 21).

Fig. 21. Number of tourists (arrivals*time spent): total (a), average time spent (b), from Italy (c), from other countries (d). Study area. 2010-2022.

Source: own elaboration based on Regione Piemonte (2023).

Indeed, the amount of tourist presences (arrivals * time spent) has been more or less stable in the Varaita Valley and it even declined in the Pellice Valley over the past twelve years. With a very low average time spent in the valleys (0.6 in the Varaita Valley and 1.2 in the Pellice Valley, fig. 21b) and with the fall in the number of Italian tourists, the Pellice Valley is now performing poorly with respect to the Varaita Valley, which seems to have maintained the inflow of Italian and foreign tourists above the 40,000 threshold.

The tourism industry in the study area is highly concentrated in a few municipalities, where the most part of the tourists tend to converge: Torre Pellice, Villar Pellice, and Bobbio Pellice in the Pellice Valley, and Sampeyre, Pontechianale, and Busca in the Varaita Valley (fig. 22).

Fig. 22. Numer of tourists. Study area. 2022.

Source: own elaboration based on Regione Piemonte (2023).

Destination for a high demand of short-term or one-day visits, the two valleys might find good opportunities of development by incentivizing solutions to prolong tourists' stay in the region. This might entail exploring strategies to promote the use of information and communication technology to market hybrid solutions integrating short-stay holiday time with periods of remote work.

Broadband internet access

The development of new solutions, or the improvement of what already is the economic fabric of the study area, requires adequate technologies and infrastructure. Information and communication technology, in this sense, is fundamental. Indeed, In the Pellice Valley the percentage of households with broadband access to the internet is around 80%, whereas in the Varaita Valley, the percentage is lower than 60% (fig. 23).

Although sufficient to perform a series of tasks, basic broadband speed might not be sufficient to support newer sorts of technologies and devices. However, faster internet connections are still very limited in the study area, thus limiting the possible adoption of new technologies. From a geographical perspective, the municipalities that still lack a proper broadband connectivity are the ones located at the end of the Varaita Valley (fig. 24), a region already subject to several disadvantages underlined in the previous sections of this report.

Fig. 23. Households with broadband access. Study area. 2022.

Source: AGCOM (2022).

Fig. 24. Households with basic broadband internet access. Study area. 2022.

Source: AGCOM (2022).

D) Needs and criticalities

From the analysis presented in the previous section, we obtain a preliminary list of potential needs and estimated resources that that study area has. The objects included in the list are the ones highlighted by the quantitative analysis, and, therefore, they should be interpreted as mere “signals” of possible issues/opportunities that a qualitative research stage in the study area should clarify.

Needs - criticalities

Before introducing a brief list of needs and criticalities that emerge from the analysis, it is important to highlight how the population in the study area has been changing over the past years. Changes in population size and structure also involve a socio-cultural dimension connected to migration flows (of both nationals and foreigners) that a quantitative study cannot detect, but that might be fundamental to understand what are the real needs and motivations of people moving to the Pellice and Varaita Valleys. Also the progressive ageing of the population (especially in the case of the Pellice Valley and a few municipalities in the ending part of the Varaita Valley) is surely modifying the perception of people about needs and criticalities, and this aspect should also be object of an on-field qualitative investigation.

However, from a general perspective, we can assert that in order to promote both economic and social vitality, for the municipalities in the study area it would be important to improve the access to higher education, by incentivizing their inhabitants to attend university courses, and/or by incentivizing students who left the valleys to study in Turin, Cuneo or elsewhere to come back to the valley after their graduation, or by attracting highly-educated immigrants.

Of course, to attract immigrants and their families, the schooling and pre-schooling systems of the valleys would need to improve, for instance through the restructuring of outdated facilities, and through extended guarantees that in the medium-long term, the system will be maintained functional (thus allowing immigrant families to plan over several years their re-settling in the valleys).

In the meantime, possible solutions should be discussed to reduce the need and the cost of private transportation for both education or work. The physical infrastructure connecting people to services needs to be effective, but mobility solutions need to be both environmentally and cost-efficient. Hybrids systems of private/communitarian mobility might be thought of as part of a general mobility plan for both the valleys.

Access to basic services needs to be maintained and improved where not sufficient. In the case of the Pellice Valley, there is a need to increase the number of family physicians, while the need for transportation between both the valleys and the health districts in Pinerolo and Saluzzo needs to be answered to through the general mobility plan introduced above. From the standpoint of commercial and other services, the need of the study area is not to stop a decline, but to avoid it. In other words, it is highly needed an assessment of the critical demographic thresholds that might compromise the commercial and service fabric of several portions of both valleys, and in particular of the Varaita one. It has to be expected, that both the financial viability of services and the profitability of commerce will collapse quickly when the population of users and clients decreases below a certain threshold. This issue needs to be anticipated and measures should be put in place to prevent the commerce and service “desertification” of scarcely-populated municipalities.

Attractiveness and economic vitality also depend on the number of higher-value added activities, capable not only to generate more profits (and possibly investments), but also higher salaries. This of course requires the

development of the necessary infrastructure, in particular internet connection via broadband networks, an asset that needs to be improved especially in the Varaita Valley. On the other hand, one of the traditional sectors of the mountain economy, the agricultural-forestry one, would benefit from the introduction of “innovative” business forms, so that the large share of agricultural activities that is currently unable of producing revenues sufficient to remunerate one worker, might be reduced. It would be important also to investigate further the condition of laborers inside the valley and in the clusters at the entrance of the valleys where the employments are concentrated to better assess their expectations and needs with respect to the relationship between their work and their housing conditions, transport requirements and their costs.

Finally, both valleys included in the study area need to put in place strategies to contrast, and possibly reverse, the underperformance of the tourism sector. Of course, the COVID-19 crisis has caused many disruptions in local tourism markets, but to re-value one of the most important industries in mountainous areas, it is necessary to deepen our understanding of the strengths, the opportunities, and the risks that local tourism operators have.

Resources - opportunities

The first element that might be considered as a resource for the study area, is its demography. In particular, in terms of demographic trends, the two valleys have shown a higher resilience, and diverging trends with respect to the negative evolution of regional and national demographic indicators. The Varaita Valley, in particular, has a “young” component that should be recognized, analyzed, and possibly valorized. Connected to this first point, there is the question of immigration, as immigration in the study area, as well as in Piedmont or in Italy, is the engine of population growth. On the other hand, the Pellice Valley represents a special case, where the human capital (in terms of education) is significantly developed (especially in a few municipalities). It would be relevant to explore if and to what extent these resources work as attractors for other individuals and households, motivating them to choose their valley when relocating from the towns in the plane. A burden that might be thought of as a resource is the orography of the study area. With a few road connections from residential municipalities to the municipalities where schools and jobs are located, communitarian or hybrid transportation systems might be more cost-effective than elsewhere. However, further research on this is needed, perhaps integrating pilot studies to demonstrate viability and scalability.

Another resource of the study area, is its “non-marginality”. It is clear how infrastructural connections between Pinerolo, Turin and the Pellice Valley might be of great importance for the development of the valley itself. However, also the Varaita valley does maintain an infrastructure sufficient to guarantee distributed access to basic services to its inhabitants, including health care and commerce.

Such a “vitality” can also be inferred from the very low unemployment rates that the two valleys have. A characteristic that is surely connected with the improvement of the net businesses balance, that after the dramatic fall of the years 2011-2012, has been improving year after year, becoming positive from 2019 onwards. Economic “vitality” is expected to produce investments at some point in time, investments that in the case of the study area might be directed to the exploitation of the massive built capital that has been abandoned over the past seventy years and that is still awaiting valorization.

Finally, the main resource and opportunity for both valleys is the re-valorization of their natural beauties, their history, and their cultures through a re-organization of the tourism sector.

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